

Multistage electro dialysis for desalination of natural seawater

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HIGHLIGHTS

- Natural seawater desalination using multistage electro dialysis
- Multivalent permeable membranes remove more magnesium.
- Multivalent permeable membranes decrease the energy consumption.
- Long-run desalination performance of ED was assessed over 18 days.

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ABSTRACT

Electro dialysis (ED) is receiving increasing attention as promising technology for seawater desalination. However, most of the ED investigations are typically performed using artificial NaCl solutions, while the effect of multivalent ions (such as Mg²⁺ and Ca²⁺) on membrane scaling and resistance has been so far overlooked. In this work, we investigate the influence of multivalent ions in seawater on the desalination performance of multistage ED. In particular, natural seawater was used as feed solution, and two different strategies were compared, i.e. by using conventional cation exchange membranes (CEMs), as well as CEMs with preferential removal of multivalent ions. For both CEMs, we found that the removal of calcium and magnesium was higher compared to that of sodium and no effect due to operation at low current density was observed. More magnesium was removed with the multivalent ion permeable CEM. Starting from ~27 g/l (i.e. inlet concentration of the natural seawater source), the upscaled multistage ED system produced a continuous diluate concentration of 1.9 g/l. The system performance was stable over 18 days, with an average energy consumption of 3 kWh/m³, demonstrating the potential of multistage ED seawater desalination.

1. Introduction

Desalination technologies have been optimized extensively over the past decades, resulting in energy consumptions for seawater desalination ranging between 3 and 4 kWh/m³ [1]. In some cases, specific energy consumptions lower than 3 kWh/m³ have been reported for some seawater reverse osmosis (SWRO) studies [2], while large-scale SWRO plants have reached nowadays values in the range of 3.5–4.5 kWh/m³, including pre- and post-treatment [3]. Despite such significant reduction in energy consumptions over the past two decades, seawater desalination technologies still remain highly energy intensive, compared to the minimum energy demand [2,4–6].

Electro dialysis (ED) is an electrochemical process based on the selective separation of cations and anions by the effect of an electric field through a series of ion exchange membranes (IEMs). ED is nowadays mostly used on industrial scale for selective removal of ions from aqueous solutions and for brackish water desalination [7,8]. Beside these conventional applications, ED and ED-based technologies (such as reverse electro dialysis (RED), and bipolar electro dialysis, BMED) have been widely investigated in the past decade, suggesting novel applications as well as coupling of membrane processes to increase the overall process efficiency, e.g. using hybrid reverse electro dialysis (RED)/ED [9], or RED/RO configurations [10].

Despite the flexibility of the technology and the variety of

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application, ED is generally considered to be too energy-intensive for seawater desalination [11]. In our previous studies we experimentally evaluated different ED configurations for seawater desalination using a single-stage ED, an electrically segmented ED configuration and an hydraulically staged (i.e. multistage) ED configuration [12–14]. In particular with the multistage ED we were able to achieve desalination of a 510 mM NaCl solution (representing the salinity of seawater) at a water recovery of 41% and an energy consumption of 2.2 kWh/m³ [14]. Besides experimental studies, also some modeling work on multistage ED has been recently reported [15,16]. These efforts contributed to renewed interest in ED to produce drinking water from seawater. Although the performance of ED using artificial seawaters is already reported by some authors [17], an experimental investigation of (multistage) ED under real conditions (i.e., using natural seawater) is still lacking.

Seawater consists of a complex matrix of organic and inorganic substances [18]. The presence of multivalent ions in seawater increases the electrical resistance of ion exchange membranes (IEMs). Due to their higher valence, multivalent ions ‘bridge’ multiple fixed charges in the IEMs resulting in an increase in electrical resistance [19]. Besides this, multivalent ions bring the risk of scaling, i.e. precipitation and deposition of their salts, due to the low solubility limits of multivalent ions in water.

So far, only one experimental study mimicking natural seawater exists for the production of drinking water [17]. In that experimental study, artificial seawater (containing multivalent ions) was used in a two-stage multistage ED configuration at a relatively high energy consumption of 6.6 kWh/m³. Moreover, the emphasis was on salt removal in general and not on understanding the influence of multivalent ions on the desalination performance specifically. Studies to understand the importance of multivalent ions are conducted at single stack level in batch operated systems rather than in multistage systems [20–22]. Moreover, authors often use equimolar concentrations of mono- and multivalent ions, i.e. ion mixtures that do not represent natural seawater concentrations. Few studies have also been reported on the effect of multivalent ions on ED performance especially focusing on cation exchange membranes (CEMs), since CEMs are mostly affected by the presence of multivalent ions [23–27].

The presence of multivalent ions causes an increase in resistance of the IEMs and induces scaling. A possible scenario to prevent these phenomena is pretreatment of the feed stream to remove multivalent ions before the feed stream is further desalinated. However, implementing additional pre-treatment technologies to remove multivalent ions (e.g. by using ion exchange resins) is in general undesired from an economical perspective, as it will cause increasing operational costs. Instead, selective removal of multivalent ions can potentially be performed within the ED system itself. In this way we perform two-stage ED desalination with each stage having a specific targeted removal of multivalent ions (stage 1) and monovalent ions (stage 2). Building on our previous work on multistage ED [12–14], we theorize that the selection of IEMs combined with the individually optimized operation of stages in a multistage system provides flexibility to mitigate the difficulties associated with the presence of multivalent ions in the desalination of natural seawater. By using a multistage ED system, the type of membranes as well as the driving force (electric potential difference) and flow velocity can be tuned independently for each single stage. Literature describes that preferential removal of specific ions may be achieved by operation at low current densities [28,29] and/or low applied voltage [20–22,30]. Preferential removal of multivalent ions can also be achieved by using membranes that preferentially permeate multivalent ions [19,31]. Such so called ‘multivalent ion permeable’ IEMs have been previously tested for reverse electrodialysis applications [23,25,32], but are not considered yet for application in desalination using ED.

Despite the amount of literature on the use of electrodialysis with concentrated electrolyte solutions, most of the experimental

investigation used artificial mixtures, while the effect of natural seawater under ED working conditions have not been explored.

The aim of this work is to investigate the performance of a multistage ED system for seawater desalination on pilot-scale and under real conditions, i.e. using natural seawater as feed solution. In particular, we investigate the effect of multivalent ion removal in the first ED stage, and the use of low water-permeable membranes in the last ED stage to mitigate the effect of osmosis and increase the overall desalination performance.

First, we investigate the effect of current density on multivalent ion removal by either using a multivalent permeable CEM or a standard commercial CEM (reference) in the first ED stage, both membranes supplied by Fujifilm. Second, we test the effect of feed solution composition on the limiting current density and desalination performance for these two ED stacks equipped with Fujifilm membranes. A third stack is equipped with Neosepta IEMs, these membranes are extensively described in literature as well as their interactions with multivalent ions [7,28,29,33,34]. We continue this investigation by testing the ED performance using natural seawater for five days. Based on the outcomes of these experiments, the most suitable membranes are selected and an upscaled multistage ED configuration using natural seawater is built and operated for 18 days. On a daily basis, we determine the limiting current density per stage to find the maximum desalination rate of the system and to evaluate the potential of multistage ED for seawater desalination.

2. Experimental setup and procedure

2.1. First stage membrane comparison from artificial to natural seawater

2.1.1. Stack configuration

Three stacks of the same size were built and assembled using different membrane types. In particular, the first stack was equipped with Fujifilm Type 10 CEMs, a second stack was equipped with Fujifilm Type T1 CEMs (multivalent permeable membranes). Both stacks were equipped with the same type of AEMs (Type 10, Fujifilm Manufacturing Europe B.V., the Netherlands). Moreover, a third stack was built for further comparison using membranes from a different manufacturer (Neosepta CSE/ASE, Astom-Corporation, Japan). The three stacks were operated in parallel under the same feed conditions, i.e. each representing a first stage in a multistage configuration. Each stack had an active area of 100 × 100 mm² per membrane. All conventional ED stacks (REDstack B.V., the Netherlands) were equipped with 10 cell pairs and 0.260 mm gasket integrated spacers (Deukum GmbH, Germany). The stacks were fed in cross-flow. Each cell pair consisted of one anion exchange membrane (AEM) and one cation exchange membrane (CEM). Moreover, additional CEMs (Neosepta CSE, Astom-Corporation, Japan) were placed as shielding membranes adjacent to each electrode compartment to prevent leakage of electrode rinse solution into the feed compartments. These shielding membranes were specifically selected for their high selectivity towards sulphate [35].

The endplates of the stacks contained titanium electrodes (mesh size 1.8 m²/m²) coated with Ru/Ir mixed metal oxide (MAGNETO Special Anodes B.V., the Netherlands) with an area of 98 × 98 mm². The shielding membrane and the endplate were separated using a 1 mm silicon gasket (Eriks B.V., the Netherlands), while the electrode compartments were filled with a woven PETEX 07-670/52 spacer (Sefar AG, Switzerland).

2.1.2. Feedwater

Experiments in the laboratory were performed by using a NaCl solution and artificial seawater with the same total equivalent concentration ($C_t = 388$ meq/l). Firstly, the ED stacks were tested using a 388 mM NaCl solution using technical-grade NaCl (Regenit, Frisia Zout B.V., the Netherlands). Secondly, an artificial seawater solution representing the ion composition of the natural seawater source (Wadden Sea, the

Netherlands) was tested. The solution contained a mixture of monovalent (Na^+ , Cl^-) and multivalent (Mg^{2+} , Ca^{2+} , SO_4^{2-}) ions, with the same equivalent concentration as in natural seawater source (Wadden Sea, the Netherlands) (Table 1). These ions represent >99.8% of the ionic composition of seawater [18], while the presence of other ions with concentration < 5 meq/l (e.g. K^+) have been neglected. The solution was prepared using the following salt concentrations: 258 mM NaCl, 3 mM NaHCO_3 , 17 mM Na_2SO_4 , 16 mM $\text{CaCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 31 mM $\text{MgCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (all salts > 99% purity, VWR chemicals). Table 2 shows the properties of cations that influence migration through the compartments and through the membranes. Contrary to experiments with artificial seawater, in the natural feed water experiments, where the aim is to desalinate to drinking water concentrations, potassium concentrations are measured. Potassium contributes to the TDS of drinking water, but from the point of health-based guidelines there is no guideline value defined for potassium in drinking water [36].

The ED stacks were finally tested by feeding natural seawater in real environment at the REDstack Blue Energy testing facility (Afsluitdijk, the Netherlands). At the testing facility seawater was first pumped to a filtration section including 20 μm drum filters, followed by 75–25 μm and 25–1 μm cartridge filters, and by a granular activated carbon filter to prevent fouling by larger particles and to remove organics substances.

In the laboratory experiments feed water was pumped through the ED stacks with the same feed flow velocity for both the diluate and the concentrate streams by using diaphragm pumps (Grundfos DDA220, Denmark). The feed flow velocity was set to 1 cm/s for all experiments. The pulsation of the pumps was leveled out using a pulsation damper (PDS250 PVC/FKM, Prominent GmbH, Germany).

In the pilot testing facility, stacks were operated continuously to observe the behavior over five days; for this purpose, the diluate and concentrate streams were fed with peristaltic pumps (Masterflex, USA). For all experiments, an aqueous solution of 0.15 M Na_2SO_4 , was used as electrode rinse solution with a flow rate of 200 ml/min per electrode compartment (~ 3 cm/s) by using a peristaltic pump (Masterflex, USA). For every experiment at different operational conditions, new electrode rinse solutions were employed.

2.1.3. Experimental procedure

Firstly, the effect of current density on multivalent ion removal was investigated using two stacks with different types of CEM (Fujifilm Type 10 and Fujifilm T1, respectively), while using the same type of AEM (Fujifilm AEM Type 10). A power source (SM70-AR24, Delta Elektronika, the Netherlands) was used to apply different current densities to the stacks fed with artificial seawater solutions (composition in Table 1). The outlet composition of the diluate and concentrate was determined by ion chromatography (Metrohm Compact IC Flex 930, the Netherlands). The conductivity was measured using a conductivity meter (Multimeter 3320 + TetraCon 325, WTW-Xylem).

Secondly, the effect of feed solution composition on limiting current density (LCD) was investigated for three different stacks. Thirdly, experiments with natural seawater were performed for a period of 5 days. During this period on daily basis, a current-voltage (I-V) curve was measured and during the remaining time (23 h/d) the stacks were operated at a constant current density of 100 A/m² (i.e., in the under-

Table 1

Typical seawater (Wadden Sea) composition at the REDstack Blue Energy testing facility (Afsluitdijk, The Netherlands). Data provided by REDstack B.V.

	Cations			Anions		
	[mmol/l]	[mg/l]	[meq/l]	[mmol/l]	[mg/l]	[meq/l]
Na^+	294	6770	294	Cl^-	351	12,449
Ca^{2+}	16	626	32	HCO_3^-	3	168
Mg^{2+}	31	753	62	SO_4^{2-}	17	1620
Total	341	8149	388		371	14,238

Table 2

Physical properties at 25 °C of most abundant cations in seawater.

Properties	K^+	Na^+	Ca^{2+}	Mg^{2+}
Diffusion coefficient at infinite dilution $\cdot 10^{-5}$ [cm^2/s] [37]	1.96	1.33	0.79	0.71
Crystal radius [\AA] [38]	1.33	0.95	0.99	0.65
Stokes radius [\AA] [38,39]	1.25	1.84	3.10	3.49
Hydration number [-] [40]	2.69	4.03	3.64	5.33
Charge density [C/mm^3] [41]	11	24	52	120

limiting current regime) and in electro dialysis reversal (EDR) mode, i. e., by switching the electrodes polarity every 30 min. Results for ion composition of the 5-day experiment were averaged.

For all LCD measurements, the LCD value was found using the Cowan and Brown method [42,43]. During all experiments, the voltage was measured using Ag/AgCl reference electrodes (QM711X, ProSense, the Netherlands) at the inlet of the electrode compartments. The reference electrodes were connected to a high impedance pre-amplifier (EX06, Ext-Ins Technologies, the Netherlands) and a digital multimeter (34461A, Keysight Technologies, USA). From the measured voltage, the voltage per cell pair was calculated, assuming the contribution of the extra shielding membrane is negligible from 10 cell pairs onwards.

The resulting outlet flow rates were measured for both diluate and concentrate at the outlet of the last stage. These flow rates were measured by manually measuring the outlet flow for at least 2 min, and by estimating the corresponding water transport taking into account the density of solution and the mass balance between diluate and concentrate. From the diluate outlet flowrate and the measured voltage between the reference electrodes (excluding electrode reactions), the energy consumption was calculated. Pumping energy was considered not significant in these small scale stacks, i.e. below 1% of the total energy consumption, thanks to the relatively low pressure drops at the feed flow velocities [13].

2.2. Upscaled multistage ED configuration using natural seawater

2.2.1. Multistage configuration

After previous experiments on the first ED stage, membranes were selected to be installed in the first stage of the upscaled multistage ED configuration. In this multistage configuration, we used three serially connected stacks each with an active area of $220 \times 220 \text{ mm}^2$ per membrane. The overall layout of the configuration is presented in Fig. 1.

The ED cross-flow stacks (REDstack B.V., the Netherlands) were built by using a decreasing amount of cell pairs ($N_1 = 100$, $N_2 = 50$, $N_3 = 25$), resulting in corresponding feed flow velocities of $v = 0.5$, 1.0, and 2 cm/s in the stages (deviations due to water transport through the membranes are not taken into account). The increased feed flow velocity in later stages is beneficial since it allows also higher limiting current densities in later stages and the water recovery is increased by the lower water diffusion from diluate to concentrate due to shorter residence times [14,42,44,45].

In the first stack Fujifilm Type 10 AEMs and Type T1 CEMs were installed. Those membranes are homogeneous IEMs based on a three-dimensional structure of inert polyolefin fibers as substrate, with quaternary ammonium or sulfonic groups as fixed charges (for AEMs and CEMs, respectively) [33]. The Fujifilm Type T1 membranes were selected because of their high transport for more multivalent ions over monovalent ions which prevent the increase of electrical resistance in subsequent stages [23,25]. In the second stack, Fujifilm Type 10 CEMs were installed because of their low resistance and high permselectivity which make them very suitable to transfer large amounts of monovalent ions. In the third stage, where osmotic water transport through the membranes may become a significant factor, Type 2 AEMs and Type 2 CEMs (Fujifilm Manufacturing Europe B.V., the Netherlands) were installed because of their low water permeability properties. In previous

Fig. 1. Schematic representation of the upscaled multistage ED experimental setup at the pilot testing facility, the diluate (blue) and concentrate (red). The electrolyte rinse solution (yellow) flows from the anolyte to the catholyte of the first electrode pair and subsequently to the anolyte and catholyte of the next electrode pairs. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

work we proved the benefit of installing Type 2 membranes in the last stage(s) [14]. As shielding membranes, Type 10 CEMs (Fujifilm Manufacturing Europe B.V., the Netherlands) were installed. The membrane properties for each type, as provided by the manufacturer, are listed in Table 3. The distance between adjacent membranes was fixed by gasket integrated woven spacers with a thickness of 0.260 mm and a porosity of 79% (Deukum GmbH, Germany). Endplate assemblies as described in Section 2.1 were also used in the upscaled multistage configuration. Electrodes with the same specifications were used for the upscaled multistage, but in this case with a larger active area of $215 \times 215 \text{ mm}^2$.

2.2.2. Feedwater

The ED configuration was fed with pretreated natural seawater from the Wadden Sea, as described in Section 2.1. The feed water was pumped through the ED stacks with the same feed flow velocity at both the diluate side and the concentrate side using diaphragm pumps (Grundfos DDA220, Denmark). The pulsation of the pumps was leveled out by using a pulsation damper (PDS250 PVC/FKM, Prominent GmbH, Germany).

The electrodes were rinsed by recirculating an aqueous solution containing 0.15 M Na_2SO_4 using a flow rate of 600 ml/min ($\sim 4 \text{ cm/s}$) by a diaphragm pump (Grundfos DDA220, Denmark). For every experiment at different operational conditions or after 5 days, new electrode rinse

solutions were employed.

The conductivity was measured with an inline conductivity meter (Type 8228, Burkert, Germany) at the inflow of the diluate and concentrate stream of the first stage and at the outflow of the diluate and concentrate stream of consecutive stage. The pressure was measured with a pressure sensor (MIDAS SW, JUMO GmbH, Germany) at the same location as the conductivity. The electrical potential or current was applied and measured using individual power sources for every stage (stage 1 and 2 SM70-AR24, stage 3: SM100-AR75, Delta Elektronika B. V., the Netherlands).

2.2.3. Experimental procedure

The upscaled multistage ED system was investigated using natural seawater as inflow. Due to the variable salinity of the natural seawater source in time, once per day, an LCD experiment per stage was carried out. The LCD experiment was carried out every time with a switched electrode polarity, also referred to as reversed-LCD (r-LCD). After determining the LCD of the first stage, the first stage was operated at 90% of the determined LCD. Subsequently, after the LCD was determined for the second stage also the second stage was operated at 90% of the determined LCD value. Finally, the same was done for the third stage, so that all stages were operated at 90% of their respective LCDs, which may be considered as the operation at which the maximum desalination degree is obtained. Once all stages were operated at this level, samples were taken to determine the outlet ion composition of each stage. The ion composition was measured using ion chromatography (Metrohm Compact IC Flex 930, the Netherlands). After the daily LCD measurements per stage and operation at 90% LCD for the measurement of the maximum desalination degree, the stacks were operated at 50% of the LCD for the remainder of the day (i.e., $\sim 20 \text{ h}$ of continuous operation) with a polarity switch every 30 min. This relatively low constant current per stage was chosen to guarantee safe operation and continuous production of a desalinated water at any inlet fluctuation possible.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Effect of current density on multivalent ion removal

The effect of current density on multivalent cation removal was investigated for two lab-scale stacks with different CEMs, i.e. Type 10 (standard) and Type T1 (multivalent permeable). Fig. 2 shows the desalination behavior of the different stacks as function of the current density for the removal of cations (Fig. 2a) and anions (Fig. 2b) from the

Table 3

Properties of ion exchange membranes used in the multistage ED applied for desalination of natural seawater (data provided by the manufacturer).

	Permselectivity ^a [%]	Water permeability [ml/ $\text{m}^2 \cdot \text{h} \cdot \text{bar}$]	Resistance ^b [$\Omega \cdot \text{cm}^2$]	Dry thickness [μm]
Fujifilm CEM Type T1 [25]	90	15	1.7	120
Fujifilm CEM Type 10	99	6.5	2.0	135
Fujifilm AEM Type 10	95	6.5	1.7	125
Fujifilm CEM Type 2	96	3.5	8	160
Fujifilm AEM Type 2	95	3.0	5	160

^a Based on the membrane potential measured over the membrane between 0.05 M and 0.5 M KCl solutions at 25 °C.

^b Measured in a 0.5 M NaCl solution at 25 °C.

Fig. 2. Effect of current density for two different types of CEMs on: a) cation removal from diluate outlet; b) anion removal from diluate outlet; c) corresponding conductivity in both concentrate and diluate outlet; d) corresponding voltage per cell pair. AEMs are similar for both stacks. The dotted lines are added to guide the eye.

diluate. Fig. 2c shows the corresponding conductivity of the diluate and concentrate compartments and Fig. 2d shows the corresponding voltage per cell pair.

Fig. 2a shows the highest relative removal for calcium, followed by magnesium and finally sodium for any tested current density. The slope for calcium decreases at the higher current densities. This indicates that calcium, due to its lower initial concentration, is depleted faster in the boundary layer compared to the other cations. Fig. 2a also shows that at higher current densities the sodium removal accelerates when the calcium removal rate decreases, indicating a surplus of sodium ions present in the boundary layer. This means that preferential removal of calcium can be achieved especially when the systems are operated at lower current densities, up to 200 A/m². The magnesium removal increases linearly with current density. This means that for the tested conditions (current density, feed flow velocity, and ion concentrations), there is no transport limitation nor enhancement of magnesium transport. Cation removal is the highest for calcium followed by magnesium and the lowest for sodium, which is similar to the findings of Sosa et al. [29] who used different membranes. The removal of magnesium scales linearly with the current density, contrary to what was found by others [20–22,28,29,46]. This is explained by the fact that our experiments are carried out in a continuous way rather than in recirculation mode in a batch configuration. In continuous operation, the desalination degree, i. e., the concentration gradient between the diluate and the concentrate compartments, stays small when compared to batch experiments. Fig. 2c shows a maximum desalination degree of 32% (based on conductivity).

At such low desalination degrees, there are only little transport limitations due to the abundant availability of salt ions in the bulk of the feed solutions. In batch experiments [28,29], the solutions are recirculated until the desired desalination degree is obtained. That means that the concentration gradient over the membrane is progressing over time and the diluate solution is further depleted in the boundary layer. This depletion, especially that of the larger multivalent ions, causes transport limitations at higher desalination degrees.

When we compare the behavior of the different CEMs used in our study, we observe similar removal rates for both CEMs for calcium and sodium, independent of the type of membrane. For magnesium this is different and membrane Type T1 (multivalent permeable membrane) shows on average a 15% higher magnesium removal rate compared to the standard Type 10 membrane. The type of CEM thus makes it possible to tune magnesium removal rates.

The standard CEM (Type 10) can transfer cations with a smaller stokes radius, i.e. sodium and calcium, but once an ion with a larger stokes radius and a higher charge density (e.g. magnesium, see Table 2 for cation properties) migrates through the membrane, this ion bridges and shields the fixed charges of the membrane, thus increasing the resistance of this standard CEM.

The multivalent ion permeable membrane (Type T1) is constructed such that large, high charge density divalent cations can only interact weakly with the fixed negative charges in the CEM [23]. This limits strong interactions between the mobile counter ion and the fixed charged groups of the membrane, thus preventing an increase in

membrane resistance. The CEM Type T1 has a relatively open polymer membrane matrix with larger free volume elements [15], especially impacting and enhancing the transport of especially magnesium. The transport of calcium, although also a larger divalent cation, is hardly influenced because calcium has a much lower charge density than magnesium. Sodium, is clearly smaller and has a lower charge density than magnesium and calcium, also, sodium shows comparable transport rates through both membranes. Clearly, a less dense membrane structure especially promotes the transport rate of the inherently slower ion, i.e. magnesium, while it hardly impacts the transport of other ions that are already faster, i.e. sodium and calcium. As a result of this lower electric resistance of the Type T1 CEM and improved migration rate of magnesium, a lower voltage is measured for the stacks containing these multivalent-ion permeable membranes (Fig. 2d).

Fig. 2c shows that both stacks (equipped with Type 10 and Type T1 CEMs) show for the same current density the same outlet conductivity for both diluate and concentrate (i.e. same desalination degree).

From these experiments it can be concluded that the current density has no significant effect on the preferential multivalent ion removal using a single pass system. To enhance preferential multivalent ion removal, in particular magnesium, a tailored membrane like Type T1 should be used. These multivalent permeable membranes remove not only about 15% more magnesium, but also use up to 20% lower voltage compared to the standard Type 10 membranes, thus proportionally reducing the energy consumption. Permeation of Mg^{2+} ions instead of binding in the CEM in combination with a slightly more open membrane

structure result in a 15% lower membrane resistance of Type T1. As a consequence, a lower voltage can be used to establish the same level of desalination resulting in a 20% decrease in energy consumption. Although equal current densities are applied for both membranes (Fig. 2), Type T1 yields a lower voltage. The produced volume of diluate depends on electro-osmosis, i.e., water transported in the hydration shell of migrating ions, which is for both stacks the same in the first stage since they show the same desalination degree. Osmosis, i.e., water transport induced by osmotic pressure difference over the membrane is small in the first stage because of the limited concentration difference over the membranes between the diluate and the concentrate compartment, as already shown in our previous work [12]. From this we can conclude that the denominator in the energy consumption calculation is the same and that the 20% lower voltage translates directly to an energy saving of 20% using Type T1 membranes.

Fig. 2b shows that the corresponding anion removal in the diluate is similar for both stacks, independent on the CEM type. Since the same AEMs are used in both stacks, the removal of anions is not impacted by the type of CEM used.

3.2. Effect of feed solution on limiting current density

We further investigated the effect of the origin of the feed solution on the limiting current density for stacks equipped with different membrane types. Feed solutions tested were artificial NaCl solution, artificial seawater, and natural seawater and experiments with stacks equipped

Fig. 3. Effect of feed composition (NaCl solution, A-SW (artificial seawater), and N-SW (natural seawater) on limiting current density for ED stacks equipped with different membranes: a) Fujifilm Type 10; b) Fujifilm Type T1; c) Neosepta; d) Comparison of limiting current density (LCD) values for the investigated membranes and feed composition. The dotted lines are added to guide the eye. The horizontal dotted lines in plots (a–c) indicate the estimated LCD value.

with CEMs commercially available Type 10, sample Type T1 or commercial Neosepta IEMs were investigated. First, the LCD was determined to determine the maximum desalination degree of each stack. Afterwards, the ion removal was investigated at an equal current density for all stacks at 100 A/m^2 (i.e. well below the LCD). Fig. 3 shows for each stack the I-V curve and the corresponding LCD value.

In agreement with literature Fig. 3 shows that all investigated membranes give the highest LCD value for the NaCl solution [47,48]. The tests with artificial seawater show for all membranes lower LCD values due to the presence of multivalent ions. As we used the same total equivalent concentration in all feed solutions (Table 1), this implies that the molar concentration from the ion mixtures and seawater solutions is somewhat lower compared to the NaCl solution with monovalent ions only. Hence, the conductivity for the NaCl solution (37 mS/cm) is slightly higher for the seawater solutions ($\sim 35 \text{ mS/cm}$). That implies that once multivalent ions are used and the same equivalent amount of charge is transported, there is a lower ion concentration in the bulk of the solution with artificial seawater compared to a solution with NaCl ions only. This implies that ion depletion at the membrane interface is stronger in a solution with multivalent ions. Since Type 1 CEMs are capable to transport magnesium at a higher rate, the LCD is in this case less affected by the presence of these multivalent ions.

Natural seawater experiments show slightly higher LCD values than artificial seawater solution experiments, except for membrane Type T1 where the LCD value for seawater is considerably lower. This is attributed to the variation in salinity and composition of the natural seawater source which varies over time and was at the time of the experiments higher than the originally anticipated salinity on which the artificial seawater solution was based on. The salinity of the natural seawater source was in the range of $404 \pm 42 \text{ mM}$ during these experiments only.

Fig. 4 shows the relative cation removal at a constant current density of 100 A/m^2 , which was chosen as it is clearly in the under-limiting regime for all membranes and feed solution types investigated.

Fig. 4 shows for all stacks similar calcium removal, while the magnesium removal for the stack with Type T1 membranes seems to be slightly higher than for the other two stacks. Instead, less potassium is removed by Type T1 membranes, because the available charge is preferentially used to selectively transport magnesium. In previous experiments, using artificial seawater, potassium was neglected due to its small contribution. For the experiments with natural seawater potassium is measured, where in previous experiments sodium was the cation with the highest diffusion coefficient, in this experiment potassium has the smallest hydrated diameter and thus the highest diffusion coefficient (Table 2), therefore relatively more potassium is transported compared

Fig. 4. Relative cation removal at a current density of 100 A/m^2 and a feed flow velocity of 1 cm/s , measured as the difference between inlet and outlet concentration for three stacks with three different membrane types. Cation removal is measured every day over five days; the average values (and associated standard deviations) are displayed.

to sodium. The removal of sodium is similar for all stacks. From the voltage measured during these experiments (SI, Fig. S.1), again a decrease in voltage of 14% was measured when using the Type T1 membranes compared to the Type 10 membranes. Compared to Neosepta membranes the Type T1 membranes even showed a 26% lower voltage.

These both findings: the advantage of removing more magnesium ions in the first stage, and the lower voltage in the Type T1 stack again confirm that Type T1 membranes are very suitable to be installed in a first stage of a multistage to increase the desalination performance meanwhile lowering the energy consumption.

3.3. Upscaled multistage ED using natural seawater, a long-run experiment

An upscaled multistage ED was built using stacks with an active area of $200 \times 200 \text{ mm}^2$ with respectively 100, 50, 25 cell pairs in subsequent stages, giving a scale-up factor of 40 for the first stage and respectively 20 and 10 times for the second and third stage, respectively. Based on previous experiments, each stage was equipped with the best performing membranes for its desalination conditions. The first stage was equipped with Type T1 to remove multivalent ions and because of its low energy consumption. Type 10 was installed in stage two to account for the gross desalination. Type 2 was installed in stage three to increase the water recovery by limiting water transport due to osmosis from the diluate to the concentrate. The upscaled multistage ED system was evaluated during 18 days using natural seawater. Fig. S.2 in the SI shows the pressure drop over time. Fig. 5 shows the removal of different cations with each stage operated at 90% of its corresponding LCD value (which slightly varies over the days due to fluctuations in the composition of the natural seawater).

Fig. 5 shows a large variation in removal efficiency for all cations, especially in the first stage. This is explained by the daily changing inlet conditions and concentrations of the natural sea water. Because of this, also the limiting current density and thus the TDS changes per day, which is depicted in Fig. 7. A higher TDS allows for a higher limiting current density and vice versa. Fig. 5a shows a relatively low relative removal of sodium ions in all stages stage compared to the other cations in Fig. 5b–d. This is similar to our earlier finding in Fig. 4. Magnesium, potassium and calcium represent only approximately 15% of the total amount of cations in seawater, the 85% remaining is sodium. As a consequence relative changes in these small contributors are larger than those for sodium. Magnesium and potassium are after the first stage on average removed by respectively 70 and 65% in Fig. 5b–c. The average calcium removal is 80%. To produce drinking water the sodium content in the outlet, after stage 3 is still somewhat too high. To meet the WHO guidelines up to a five times higher sodium desalination is required (200 mg/l of sodium [49]). The guideline for calcium is met ($100\text{--}300 \text{ mg/l}$) [49]. Magnesium and potassium are not mentioned in the guidelines. The outlet content for all cations was relatively stable; this confirms the reliability of the system, and the flexibility to cope with variable inlet conditions.

Fig. 6 shows the corresponding removal of anions at 90% LCD for each stage measured during a long-run test of 18 days.

Fig. 6a shows that chloride has a similar removal compared to sodium in Fig. 5a. Chloride, as monovalent counter-ion will therefore show similar desalination behavior. The removal of chloride is between 90 and 95%, i.e. still above concentration threshold for drinking water composition according to WHO guidelines ($200\text{--}300 \text{ mg/l}$ of chloride [49]). To meet the WHO guidelines, the current outlet concentrations need to be lowered 3–4 times. Fig. 6b shows the sulphate removal, which outlet concentration meet the WHO guidelines (250 mg/l of sulphate [49]). Besides the presence of sulphate in seawater, sulphate was also present in the electrode rinse solution. These data confirm that sulphate did not leak from the electrode rinse solution to the membrane pile, because no strong or sudden decrease in removal is shown. The peak

Fig. 5. Relative removal of different cations during a long-run test performed at 90% LCD for each stage: a) sodium; b) magnesium; c) potassium; d) calcium. The dotted lines are added to guide the eye. The arrows indicate the contribution of each stage to the removal of cations from the initial feed concentration.

Fig. 6. Removal of different anions during a long-run test performed at 90% LCD for each stage: a) chloride; b) sulphate. The dotted lines are added to guide the eye.

shown at day 6 can be caused by a decrease in the inflow concentrations. However, desalination of natural seawater implies uncertainty and many parameters that cannot be controlled, making a very systematic explanation not possible. Although the performance of the first stage is not constant, stage 2 and 3 together assure a constant outlet composition for both anions, which makes the desalination system reliable.

Fig. 7 shows all the main measured output parameters, i.e. LCD both standard operation and EDR mode ("r-LCD"), inlet and outlet total dissolved solids (TDS, calculated from IC measurements), and finally the energy consumption per stage.

In Fig. 7a, stage 1 shows initially a decreasing LCD that increases after day 11. This minimum in LCD cannot be attributed to the low amount of salts present (Fig. 7c). Due to the complexity of natural water, many interconnected parameters play a role, making it impossible to give a single explanation. Many different factors can influence the membrane performance, i.e., colloidal-fouling, bio-fouling, increased membrane resistance due to multivalent ions, etc. The decreased LCD in stage 1 causes less desalination in stage 1 (Fig. 7c) and as a consequence the inflow concentration in stage 2 increases. Due to the higher salinity pumped into stage 2 and later also into stage 3, these stages increase in

Fig. 7. Operational parameters overtime for a multistage with 3 stages: a) Limiting current density over time per stage; b) Limiting current density during polarity switch (EDR mode) over time; c) Total dissolved solids (TDS) in g/l over time; d) Cumulative energy consumption, contribution expressed per stage and stage 3 gives total desalination energy consumption. The dotted lines are added to guide the eye.

LCD and thereby compensate the underperformance of stage 1. Fig. 7b shows the same behavior in the r-LCD mode.

Fig. 7c shows a varying feed concentration over the measuring days. The TDS of stage 1 is varying over time due to the daily changing LCD values, while stage 2 and 3 give a relatively constant outflow of respectively 4.8 g/l and 1.9 g/l. Fig. 7d shows that initially stage 1 takes a large share in the energy consumption. When the LCD of stage 1 lowers also the stage 1 energy consumption lowers and stage 2 and 3 are compensating this underperforming of stage 1. On system level the multistage ED system is able to produce a relatively constant outflow TDS of 1.9 g/l, while the WHO guidelines advice a concentration below 0.6 g/l [49]. The energy consumption to desalinate until 1.9 g/l was around 3 kWh/m³.

4. Conclusions

The aim of this work was to investigate the desalination performance of multistage electro dialysis system on pilot-scale using natural seawater as feed solution. In particular, we systematically investigated the performance of the system using NaCl solutions, artificial ion mixtures, as well as natural seawater as feed solutions under real operating conditions on pilot installation.

Firstly, the effect of current density on multivalent ion removal was investigated. Both membrane types (Type 10 and Type T1) showed preferential removal of calcium and magnesium for all current densities tested (0–300 A/m²), while no preferential removal was observed at low current densities (<50 A/m²). The Type T1 membranes, which have weaker interactions with multivalent ions, were able to remove up to 15% more magnesium compared to (standard) Type 10 membranes. The

removal of calcium and sodium was similar for both membrane types. When comparing the energy consumption for the two membranes, Type T1 membranes allowed to achieve outperformed, due to a, with a 20% lower energy consumption than the Type 10 membranes, mostly as result of the lower electrical resistance.

Secondly, we investigated the effect of feed solution on limiting current density. The highest LCD values were measured for NaCl solution, while the tests with artificial seawater showed a lower limiting current density. We operated the three stacks for five days using natural seawater, and also in this case the stack with Type T1 membranes removed more magnesium compared to Type 10 membranes. For these reasons, Type T1 membranes were installed in the first ED stage, to preferentially remove multivalent ions and prevent increase of the electrical resistance and membrane scaling in the other stages.

Finally, an upscaled multistage ED system was tested under real conditions using natural seawater for 18 days of operation, showing stable diluate outlet concentration during the whole testing period (1.9 g/l TDS), and an overall energy consumption of ~3 kWh/m³. Further studies should focus on four-stage multistage, in combination with different hydraulic configurations, to investigate the possibility to further reduce the energy consumption of the system.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

G.J. Doornbusch: conceptualization, methodology, investigation, visualization, writing - original draft

M. van der Wal: methodology, investigation

M. Tedesco: supervision, writing – review and editing

J.W. Post: conceptualization, supervision, writing – review and

editing, project administration, funding acquisition

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K. Nijmeijer: conceptualization, supervision, writing – review and editing

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.desal.2021.114973>.

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